

The Ductus Venous Obstruction and Awan Blue Anomaly

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The inferior vena cava (IVC) is the largest vein in the body, play an important role for carrying deoxygenated blood from the lower body to the heart.[1] It is establish by the convergence of the two common iliac veins and ascends through the abdomen, passing through the diaphragm, and emptying into the right atrium of the heart.[2]

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Diagram_of_the_human_heart_\(cropped\).svg](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Diagram_of_the_human_heart_(cropped).svg)

Ductus venosus flow refers to the blood flow through the ductus venosus, a fetal blood vessel that associate the umbilical vein to the inferior vena cava. [3]This vessel plays a critical role in fetal circulation, allowing oxygenated and nutrient-rich blood from the placenta to bypass the liver and enter the heart directly.[4]

The ductus venosus usually closes within a few minutes after birth but this may take longer in preterm neonates.[5]

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ductus_venosus#/media/File:Gray502.png

Ductus venosus flow obstruction cite to a blockage or restriction in the flow of blood through the ductus venosus, a vital fetal blood vessel.[6] This obstruction can occur due to various reasons, such as:

- Thrombosis or blood clots
- Compression by adjacent structures
- Infection or inflammation

Obstruction of ductus venosus flow can lead to severe consequences, including:

- Growth restriction: Reduced blood flow can limit fetal growth and development.
- Hypoxia: Inadequate oxygen supply can lead to hypoxia, causing damage to fetal organs and tissues.

- Heart defects: Abnormal blood flow patterns can increase the risk of congenital heart defects.
- Brain and spinal cord abnormalities: Reduced oxygenation can affect fetal brain and spinal cord development.
- Gastrointestinal anomalies: Obstruction can increase the risk of gastrointestinal malformations.
- Skeletal anomalies: Abnormal blood flow can affect fetal skeletal development.
- Chromosomal abnormalities: Ductus venosus flow obstruction has been linked to an increased risk of chromosomal abnormalities, such as trisomy 21 (Down syndrome).
- Fetal distress: Obstruction can cause fetal distress, leading to increased risk of stillbirth or neonatal complications.
- Premature birth: Ductus venosus flow obstruction can increase the risk of premature birth.
- Fetal death: In severe cases, ductus venosus flow obstruction can lead to fetal death.[7]

Sign and symptoms of Ducts Venosus Flow Obstruction in Mother:

Symptoms of ductus venosus flow obstruction in mothers may include:

- Cyanosis

- Leg pain or cramping
- Fatigue
- Shortness of breath
- Nausea and vomiting
- Chest pain or discomfort
- Swelling in the legs, ankles, or feet
- Abdominal pain or tenderness
- Headaches
- Hypertension .[8]

Assessment of Ductus Venosus flow:

In the valuation of ductus venosus flow the gestation must be 11⁺⁰ to 13⁺⁶ weeks and the CRL 45-84 mm.[9]

- The fetus should not be moving.
- A right ventral mid-sagittal view of the fetal trunk should be acquired
- Colour flow mapping should be used to indicate the umbilical vein, ductus venosus and fetal heart.
- The pulsed Doppler sample must be small (0.5-1.0 mm) to keep away contamination from the adjacent veins and it should be placed in the yellowish aliasing area
- The insonation angle must be less than 30 degrees.

- The filter must be set at a low frequency (50-70 Hz) to allow visualization of the whole waveform.
- The sweep speed must be high (2-3 cm/s) so that the waveforms are widely spread for better evaluation of the a-wave.

Ductus venous flow Doppler image

Awan Blue Anomaly and Ductus venosus flow obstruction:

Awan blue anomaly define as Ductus venosus flow obstruction can potentially lead to the brain atrophy in the fetus can have long term effects on a child even after 3 year of age. In anomaly brain cannot be shrink properly before 3 year of age. People with these type of anomaly loss of brain cell very slowly. Brain atrophy lasts a life time but symptom cannot show before a 3 year of age. Average time for getting the brain atrophy is minimum 3 year. Brain atrophy lead to the shrinkage or wasting away of brain tissue, which can result from a lack of oxygen and nutrients due to reduced blood flow.[10]

Venous ductus obstruction can cause brain atrophy by:

- Reducing oxygen and nutrient delivery to the brain
- Increasing pressure in the brain due to blood backup
- Leading to hypoxic-ischemic injury (injury due to lack of oxygen and blood flow)
- Disrupting normal brain development and growth

Phenotype and symptoms of Brain Atrophy before 3 year age:

Phenotype and symptom before 3 year of brain atrophy in child may include:

- Suddenly high fever
- Microcephaly
- Oval face shape
- Pale yellow or white cream skin color
- Bone rotation
- Chest infection
- Slow muscle movement
- Short fingers
- Short neck
- Tongue stick out of the mouth
- Shortness of breath
- Heavy or no face expression
- Almond shape eyes
- Runny nose.[11]

Neurological Problems:

Brain atrophy can result in various neurological and developmental problems, including:

- Cognitive impairment
- Motor dysfunction
- Seizures
- Developmental delays
- Cerebral palsy
- Vision and hearing impairments
- Microcephaly[12]

Blue Awan anomaly fetus case study:

Increased impedance to flow in the fetal ductus venosus at 11-13 weeks' gestation, is related fetal anomalies. Most studies inspect ductus venosus flow have classified the waveforms as normal, when the a-wave observed during atrial contraction is positive, or abnormal, when the a-wave is absent or reversed. The lodge alternative in the estimation of patient-specific risks for pregnancy complications is measurement of the pulsatility index for veins (PIV) as a continuous variable.[13]

Abnormal ductus venosus blood flow during Pregnancy:

The point of this study was to evaluate the accurate anatomy of umbilico-portal system in cases of abnormal ductus venosus flow in routine 11-13+6 weeks sonographic examinations in fetuses with low risk of chromosomal abnormalities in the 1st trimester and no anatomical anomalies in the 2nd trimester scan.[13]

A 33 year old women first presented for 11+6 week gestation with fatigue, heavy breathing and cyanosis (blue nails) without significant medical or familial disease. Doppler Ultrasound examination revealed an abnormal ductus venosus flow.[14]

Abnormal ductus venosus flow between 11 and 13+6 weeks with normal fetal anatomy can be an indicator of portal system variations.

Fetal Brain Atrophy Ultrasound case study:

A 33 year old women first presented for 11+6 week gestation. Ultrasound examination revealed a single fetus with brain atrophy and CRL 3.9 cm .Fetal cardiac activity is present with resisted growth.[15]

11+6 week ultrasound with brain atrophy

Venous ductus flow obstruction can affect fetal growth and development. The ductus venosus is a vital vessel that connects the umbilical vein to the inferior vena cava, allowing oxygenated and nutrient-rich blood to reach the fetal heart. Obstruction of this vessel can lead to brain atrophy [16]

Brain Atrophy After Birth:

A 3 year old baby present for high fever and several episode of seizure, EEG examination revealed a focal epileptic form activity.[17]

State of Patient: Awake with eyes closed & cooperative

SYSTEM OF RECORDING

This is an 32 channel digital EEG Record base on 10-20 International system of electrodes placement

PROVOCATION OF PROCEDURE

Hyperventilation & Intermittent photo stimulation

INTERPRETATION

Posterior rhythm 08-10 Hz alpha activity good amplitude & reactivity present / symmetry is not present anterior rhythm is beta activity over 14 Hz seen

ABNORMAL FINDING

Episodes of high amplitude sharp & theta wave focal activity detected over right temporo-parietal areas seen during resting & HV records

OTHERS

Eyes Movement and muscle artifacts in frontal & temporal areas Noted

HYPERVENTILATION

Not a significant response

IPS

Response was unremarkable

IMPRESSION

Abnormal The current EEG is abnormal in view of Episodes of paroxysmal burst of high amplitude sharp slow theta waves in wave focal activity detected over right temporo-parietal area seen the background is within normal limit.

CONCLUSION

The abnormality is suggestive of FOCAL epileptiform activity.

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not valid For court

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After a couple of days CT scan examination revealed diffuse moderate brain atrophy [18]

Technique: Imaging was performed with appropriately angled contiguous axial tomographic slices from the base of skull through to the vertex.
Clinical Info:

FINDINGS Prominence of cerebral sulci and gyri is seen due to diffuse atrophic brain changes. Ventricular dilatation is corresponding to sulcal atrophy. No infarct, mass or bleed is seen. No mid-line shift or evidence of brain herniation. Posterior fossa contents are normal. Bilateral CP angles are normal. Both cerebellar hemispheres appear normal. No bone lesion is seen. Visualized portion of Paranasal sinuses and orbits are normal. Pituitary fossa appears normal. No para sellar /cavernous sinus pathology is seen. Base of the skull appears normal. Both mastoids are normal. Nasopharynx is unremarkable.

IMPRESSION:

Diffuse Moderate Brain atrophy

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Sign and Symptoms After Brain Atrophy:

Brain atrophy manifest in various symptoms depending upon the affected brain region and severity of the atrophy common symptoms include:

- High fever
- Seizure
- Hypoxia
- Chronic Chest infection
- Weight loss
- Muscle atrophy
- Femoral anteversion
- Dysphagia.[19]

Conclusion:

There is no known cure for Awan Blue anomaly however different treatment option are available to manage the underlying causes and symptoms of Awan Blue anomaly. Life span of patient with Awan Blue anomaly can vary greatly depending on the underlying causes and severity.[20]

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